

Fire against Fire: 2D Computational Modelling of Wildfire In-Draft Flows for Suppression by Counter Firing

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ABSTRACT

Devastating wildfires are reported every year all over the globe and their economical, social and environmental impact can be substantial. Efficient firefighting techniques are therefore required to limit the damage they cause. Sometimes, a wildfire is too big to be fought directly and one of the few solutions available is to deprive it of fuel. This is done by using fire-breaks: strip of land without any fuel to burn. This paper focuses on a fire suppression method called counter-firing which uses fire to fight fire. The method consists in creating a fire-break by igniting a second fire ahead of the wildfire. This technique, despite being hazardous, can be very effective. Unfortunately, its mechanisms are not understood as very little research has been done on the subject. The aim of this paper is to use Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) and a 2D model to simulate the velocity field around a wildfire, putting emphasis on the in-draft flow. The in-draft is a buoyancy driven flow that pulls fresh air from the surroundings towards the wildfire. It can be very helpful to handle the counter-firing process as it can move against the main wind direction and therefore drive the counter-fire towards the wildfire. The problem considered is a wildfire in an open land subject to a cross wind. The domain is 2D, the equations are solved using the Unsteady Reynolds Averages Navier-Stokes Equations (URANS) with the $k - \epsilon$ turbulence model. The simulations gave a general shape of the in-draft flow with distance to the wildfire as well as the influence of the wind velocity and the intensity of the fire. The model was able to predict some general results in agreement with previous studies. It also showed some non-physical flow behavior that can be explained by the dimensionality of the domain. This is the main conclusion of the present study: a wildfire in the cross wind cannot be modeled in 2D but 3D is required.

KEYWORDS: Wildfires, Suppression, In-draft, CFD

NOMENCLATURE LISTING

Φ	heat release rate (MW)	h_0	reference height (m)
Φ_l	heat release rate per unit length (MW/m)	U_{wind}	horizontal wind velocity at h_0 (m/s)
Φ^*	dimensionless heat release rate	α	wind velocity profile parameter
λ	radiative fraction	a	length of baseline grid cells (m)
$c_{p,air}$	air heat capacity (kJ/kg)	q	ratio of length between two grid cells
ρ_{ext}	external air density (kg/m ³)	k	turbulence kinetic energy (J)
T_{ext}	external air temperature (K)	ϵ	turbulence dissipation rate (m ² /s ³)
T_f	exhaust gas temperature (K)	W	width of the domain (m)
w_f	width of the wildfire (m)	H	height of the domain (m)
\dot{m}_f	mass flow rate of exhaust gases (kg/s)	D	distance between wildfire and left boundary (m)
g	gravity acceleration (m/s ²)		

INTRODUCTION

Wildfires often have disastrous environmental and economical consequences and can be deadly. Should the fire be too big to be fought directly, indirect methods are needed. A common technique is to use fire-breaks [1], which are fuel-less strips of land the fire cannot cross. They can be already existing (eg. rivers, roads) or built rapidly before an approaching fire front. One way to clear every fuel in a place is to burn it down. To do so quickly, firefighters have to ignite a second fire called Counter-fire [2]. Counter-firing is only used

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as last resort, given the risks involved. Fortunately, the in-draft flow of the wildfire can help to handle the counter-fire. The in-draft is a buoyancy driven flow that attracts fresh air towards the wildfire entrained by the rising smoke. As such, it can move against the wind, as can be seen on Fig. 1, and drive the counter-fire towards the wildfire, creating the fire break when they meet [1]. The counter-fire has to be ignited far enough from the wildfire not to endanger the firefighters, but close enough to benefit from the in-draft. At present, the fire-control technologist can only rely on experience to decide whether counter-firing can be used, and how. Only a few guidelines based on rules of thumb [2,3] exist to assist. The purpose of this study is to numerically simulate the in-draft flow around a wildfire using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) in order to understand its behavior. The ultimate objective would have been to provide useful guidelines for firefighters. Because of the lack of experimental data though, the model can not be validated and its result can not be applied straight away. The main parameters investigated are the strength of the wind and the intensity of the fire. The simulations are performed with the commercial CFD code StarCCM+.

Fig. 1. Scheme of the physical problem modeled. The wildfire on the left is subject to a cross wind pointing right. The in-draft ahead of the wildfire moves against the wind and drives the counter-fire to the left.

METHOD

StarCCM+

CFD is a discipline which uses computing power to numerically solve the fluid mechanics equations. It is widely used in the industry as well as in academic research thanks to its ability to simulate fluid flows of very different natures. In the present paper, the CFD code StarCCM+ was chosen. Because a fire is involved, the use of a software specialized in buoyancy-driven flows would be justified. An example of such a code is Fire Dynamic Simulator 5, developed by the National Institute of Standards and Technology, USA. However, the most important phenomenon to capture is the behavior of the flow near the ground, rather than the eddies in the plume and StarCCM+ is better at simulating the boundary layer. In addition, two previous CFD simulations of the same problem have been carried out using FDS5 by Wolniki K. P. [4] and by Roxburgh R. [5]. Therefore, so this study makes it possible to compare the results from both codes.

Main assumptions

For the sake of generality and simplicity, the problem modeled is a stagnant wildfire in a flat open land subject to a cross flow representing the wind. The counter-fire is not modeled given its relative small size: its influence on the in-draft flow of the main fire is neglected. As such we are only modeling the in-draft of a fire here. This assumption has already been used in previous papers [4,5] One of the main assumptions, and the one that will be

discussed later on, is that the domain is two dimensional (2D). One axis (x) is oriented in the wind direction and the other one (y) is vertical, as depicted on Fig. 2. Although turbulence is by definition an eminently three dimensional phenomenon, this assumption was deemed reasonable as the value to be measured, that is the horizontal velocity towards the fire, is also 2D. A compromise between accuracy and complexity needs to be found and it is believed that a many things can be learned about the problem from a 2D simulation. In addition, it is a assumption already made in the two previous studies [4,5]. The reduced dimensionality permitted to significantly reduce the computational cost of the simulations.

Fig. 2. Overview of the 2D Domain and its main dimensions H, D and W . The wind follows a parabolic profile, the region of interest is ahead of the wildfire, where the in-draft move against the wind.

Geometry

The three key lengths of the model are the width W , the height H and the distance to the fire D , summarized in Fig. 2. The region of interest is located near the ground, downstream of the fire as it is the location where the in-draft fights against the wind. The domain borders have to be far enough from the fire not to interfere with the in-draft but not too far as it would be a waste of computational power. The optimum values of H, W and D were determined with a sensitivity analysis.

Fire

Combustion is not modeled since the interest lies outside in the chemical processes but in the in-draft velocity profile. The fire is modeled as a heat source. It consists of a rectangular box releasing hot air from the top surface and extracting air from the two lateral surfaces. The rate of entrainment is calculated to respect mass conservation within the fire. The velocity profile along each surface is set uniform and independent of the external flow. We also assume that the fire extracts the same amount of air on each side. These assumptions are justified since the in-draft is propelled by buoyancy rather than the boundary conditions on the fire. In addition, previous studies using Fire Dynamics Simulator[6] showed the small influence of this assumption on the overall flow behavior.

The mass flow rate of air released by the wildfire can be calculated for a given Heat Released Rate Φ (HRR), using Eq. 1 [7] that relates it to the difference of enthalpy between the cool ambient air and the hot gases.

$$\Phi(1 - \lambda) = \dot{m}_f c_{p,air}(T_f - T_{ext}) \tag{1}$$

where λ is known as the radiative fraction. Experiments showed that 0.35 is the most common value. The hot gases temperature T_f is set at 1300K as flaming combustion typically occurs in wild-land fuels at a flame temperature between 1050K and 1450K [8].

The relationship between horizontal extension of the fire w_f and the Heat Released Rate is given by the dimensionless HRR (also known as Froude number) Φ^* [7] :

$$\Phi^* = \frac{\Phi_l}{\rho_{ext} c_p T_{ext} w_f \sqrt{g w_f}} \quad (2)$$

This equation is solved taking $\Phi^* = 1$ which implies that the momentum and buoyancy forces are of the same order. It is generally the case in a natural fires [6, 7]. Combining Eq. 1 and Eq. 2, the hot gases mass flow rate \dot{m}_f and the width of the fire-line w_f can be calculated for any given HRR. The HRR considered here are between 1 MW/m and 10 MW/m. Fire-intensities greater than 10MW/m are supposed excessive and are not considered in this paper.

Wind

Due to the friction against the ground, the strength of the wind is strongly related to the height. This is the Atmospheric Boundary Layer. This friction depends to the topology of the terrain: more friction is observed in dense forests than in the middle of the sea [9]. In the scope of this study, in which neither the surface roughness or the stability of the atmosphere are known, a generic power law wind profile is adopted:

$$U = U_{wind} \left(\frac{h}{h_0} \right)^\alpha \quad (3)$$

The empirical parameter α varies from 0.1 to 0.6, depending on the weather and the time of the day. The value taken is 0.15 as it is the one encountered in a rural area and on a sunny day (the worst case in term of wildfire spreading). To support this choice, this value has already been used in other of fire coupled to wind studies [12] and is the most common used in the wind power industry.

Mesh

The high level of turbulence here requires a fine mesh in order to capture the flow. This is especially true in the region of interest near the ground and near the fire where the level of buoyancy is the highest. In these zones, the cell size has to be of a few centimeters, typically 30 cm. This value was determined thanks to a sensitivity analysis. To save computational time, the grid is made coarser away from them by a geometric mesh. The fineness of such a the mesh is controlled by only two parameters: the size of the baseline cells a and the ratio q between two cells. Figure 3 summarizes the general pattern of the mesh used.

Fig. 3. Description of the Geometric Mesh used. The baseline cells are adjacent to the top of the fire and have a length of a . q is the geometric ratio of the length of two adjacent cells.

Boundary Conditions

The boundary conditions used in this paper are summarized in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Name and details of all the boundary conditions applied on the domain.

The wind velocity profile and ambient temperature are imposed on the Upstream Boundary, on the left hand side. A no-slip wall condition is applied on the lower boundary. The velocity is imposed on the fire and so is the temperature for the exhaust. The top and right boundaries were however more difficult to define. A turbulent flow crossing an open boundary is hard to model as their influence on the internal fields is wanted null as if there were no boundary at all. Many different boundary conditions were tested. Eventually, the best solution we found was to impose the pressure to be ambient. The velocity and the temperature are extrapolated from the adjacent cells using reconstruction gradient so that their profile can develop from the inlets.

Physical model and solver

The fluid is assumed to be pure air respecting the Ideal Gas Law. A segregated method to solve the system of transport equations was chosen. A coupled approach could be justified in the present case of a buoyancy-driven flow. The segregated solver was chosen though because it runs faster and is more stable.

Turbulence modeling

The Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) equations have been used with the $k - \epsilon$ turbulence model. Turbulence modeling is one of the biggest challenges in CFD and the cause of many approximations. Direct Numerical Simulations (DNS) as well as Large Eddy Simulations (LES) have been avoided on the basis that a precise description of the flow fields at every time step is not required. A time and space average of the velocity is enough to depict the in-draft of the fire, and RANS schemes run a great deal faster than DNS or LES.

The $k - \epsilon$ model is a two equations closure of the RANS equations that relates the turbulent velocity and length scales to the kinetic energy of turbulence k and the turbulence dissipation rate ϵ . It was chosen for its simplicity and stability. Also, a good calibration of the five coefficients of the model could be found in the literature to optimize it to atmospheric flows (see Tab. 1). It is known that the $k - \epsilon$ model gives bad results in case of adverse pressure gradients but this does not happen in a fire.

Table 1. Values of the constants of the $k - \epsilon$ model

	C_μ	$C_{\epsilon 1}$	$C_{\epsilon 2}$	σ_k	σ_ϵ	source
Standard values	0.09	1.44	1.92	1.00	1.30	[13]
Values for atmospheric flows	0.033	1.176	1.92	1.00	1.30	[14]

Steady RANS failed to provide a converged solution in most configurations. Consequently, Unsteady RANS had to be used. By definition, the Reynolds Average Navier-Stokes Equations are used to compute averaged quantities, but the definition of the average is often ambiguous when it comes to turbulent flows. RANS employs *ensemble* averaging, which is different from *time* averaging when the flow is not steady. Other studies demonstrated that URANS could provide a good agreement with experimental results even for complex flows [10, 11].

RESULTS

Sensitivity Analysis

Because it was not possible to determine a priori the optimum mesh refinement and the optimum dimensions of the domain, we performed a sensitivity analysis. The influence of a , q , H , D and W was assessed. The analysis was performed with a Heat Release Rate of 10 MW (worst case) and Wind Velocity of 5 m/s, which is in the middle of the range of velocities considered. Convergence could be observed in every parameter within an error in the in-draft flow below 10%. For every parameter, the error was calculated in comparison with the result of the most expensive simulation (bigger domain dimensions and finest mesh refinement). Quantitatively, the domain was 90 m wide (W), the distance to the fire D was 60 m, the fineness of the smallest cells a was 0.3 m and the cell ratio q equal to 1.005. The Height of the domain depends on W and U_{wind} and varied between 110 and 240 m. Indeed, for the model to be applicable, the plume needs to escape the domain through the right boundary rather than the upper one. If the plume leaves the computational domain before even reaching the right end of it, the flow on the right-hand side is no longer entrained by the plume above it and is of little significance. Moreover, we observed that the minimum fire distance D was significant. That is because the boundary layer on the ground needs a certain distance to develop from the parabolic profile. Having a short distance D means imposing the wind profile directly on the fire, which over-constrains the flow. If the distance is made bigger however, the boundary layer has time to develop and the parabolic profile is not close enough to the fire to disturb it. The importance of the development of the velocity profile had already been noticed by Wolnicki [4].

Overview of the computed velocities, pressures and temperatures

Before showing the velocity measurements, it is worth looking at the velocity, temperature and pressure fields inside the domain. An overview of these fields can be seen on 5, in the case $HRR=10$ MW and $U_{wind}=5$ m/s. Below the plume of the wildfire, the flow is moving to the left, it is the in-draft.

Fig. 5. Snapshot of Velocity, Temperature and Pressure fields obtained by the simulation. The flow under the plume of the fire is reversed compared to the wind. For clarity, temperatures above 400K are not plotted on the middle snapshot.)

Quantitative measurement of the in-draft

To obtain comparable quantities, the horizontal velocity near the ground is averaged over space and time. The velocity is measured at three different heights (0.5 m, 1.0 m and 1.5 m) every 5 m from the fire up to the downstream boundary, to span the region of interest. The average value between the three heights is then taken. An representative example of the time evolution of the space averaged horizontal velocity is displayed on Fig. 6. Negative velocities means that the flow direction is opposite to that of the wind: there is an in-draft. Two regimes can be observed. During the Transient Regime (between 100 s and 200 s of physical time), the plume develops from the initial condition. The second regime can be qualified as "Stationary": the velocities keeps fluctuating around a constant value. The velocities are then averaged over 200 s of Stationary Regime.

No experimental measurements on counter-fires were available in the literature to validate or invalidate the results of this thesis. The only comparison possible is with two previous CFD simulations of the same problem: the work of Wolniki[4] and of Roxburgh[5]. Hence, the following results are informative and should not be applied for fire-fighting purposes.

Fig. 6. Example of the time evolution of the space averaged horizontal velocity measured at 5, 45, and 70 m from the fire. Negative velocities indicate a flow moving against the wind. During the transient regime, the flow develops from the initial conditions before reaching a stationary regime

General pattern

The first result presented here is the general pattern of the In-draft. A relevant simulation was chosen to illustrate this general shape of the velocity profile, taking $U_{wind}=5$ m/s and $HRR=10$ MW/m. The averaged velocity profile is presented on Fig. 7 with the standard deviation bars. The data used to calculate the standard deviations are the spaced averaged horizontal velocity measured at every time step. The fire is located at the origin of the abscissa.

Fig. 7. General velocity pattern: averaged horizontal velocity in terms of the remoteness to the fire, with standard deviation bars. The velocities are negative because they point in the direction opposite to the wind. The closer to the fire, the weaker the in-draft.

The profile can be divided in three regions: The *Near Field*, the *Intermediate Region*, and the *Far Field*. The flow in the Near Field, which only covers the first ten meters, is more affected by the fire boundary conditions than the entrainment of the plume. Given all the simplifying assumptions made on the fire boundary conditions, the Near Field is of little interest. It is followed by an Intermediate Region where the velocity increases in magnitude with the distance: the in-draft develops. In the Far Field zone, the velocity stops increasing and stabilizes around 2.2 m/s in this example.

Wind and HRR sensitivity

Then, the influence of the wind and the fire intensity was investigated. We tested five fire-intensities between 1 and 10 MW/s and five wind velocities between 1 and 7 m/s, for a total of 25 simulations which are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Results Matrix. "X" means no In-draft was created, "n/a" means model not applicable. In other cases, there is a in-draft created.

HRR (MW/m) \rightarrow	1	3	5	7	10
$\downarrow U_{wind}$ (m/s)					
1	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2	X	OK	OK	OK	OK
3.5	X	X	OK	OK	OK
5	X	X	X	OK	OK
7	X	X	X	X	X

The influence of U_{wind} is assessed keeping the HRR constant at 7 MW/m. The in-draft profile for three wind velocities are superimposed on Fig. 8. The standard deviation bars are not shown for clarity purposes. Figure 9 shows the global in-draft velocity averaged all over the region of interest in terms of the wind velocity, with the standard deviation bars. On the other hand, to evaluate the impact of the fire-line intensity, U_{wind} is set equal to 2 m/s. Likewise, the resulting in-draft profiles are plotted in Fig. 10.

Fig. 8. Averaged In-draft velocities for several wind velocities in terms of the distance from the wildfire and $HRR=7MW/m$. Standard deviation bars removed for clarity.

Fig. 9. Global in-draft velocity (averaged over x as well) in terms of U_{wind} with standard deviations bars.

Fig. 10. Averaged In-draft velocities in term of the distance from the wildfire for several HRR, $U_{wind}=2$ m/s. Standard deviation bars removed for clarity.

DISCUSSION

General flow pattern

Surprisingly, the model predicts that the closer to the wildfire, the weaker the In-draft. Intuitively, we would expect the strongest in-draft to be near the fire, as the latter is the spring of the plume and thus of the In-draft. However, here, the in-draft needs a certain distance to develop and there is almost no In-draft adjacent to the fire. This result, although not intuitive, is in accordance with the work of Wolniki [4] and Roxburgh [5]. They both predicted a region near the fire with a positive horizontal velocity. Here, the velocity is negative everywhere but this is because the model of the fire is different: the "fire-box" approximation does not allow positive velocities. This phenomenon can be explained by the entrainment of the plume. Because of the recirculation of the air, most of the air near the fire is sucked into the plume rather than in the combustion zone.

The standard deviation bars are also bigger away from the fire-line, which is another point of agreement with Wolniki and Roxburgh. To confirm this observation, time recordings of the in-draft such as the example on Fig. 6 show that the oscillations of the horizontal velocity are of a higher frequency and a smaller magnitude near the fire. This is because the high temperature gradients in the Near Field introduce a high level of buoyancy forces generating smaller, faster and more energetic eddies than at a greater distance.

As can be seen on Fig. 7, the extension of the in-draft in the Far Field seems infinite: the velocity never becomes positive after the fire no matter how wide the domain is. From a quantitative perspective, given that the influence of a 2 m/s wind on the wildfire is clearly noticeable, a 2.2 m/s in-draft is believed sufficient to drive a counter-fire toward the wildfire. The infinite extension of the in-draft in the wind direction was also predicted by Wolniki, although he predicted a Far Field zone 20 m away from the fire instead of 60m here. Unfortunately, it means that the model in this paper cannot predict the maximum extension of the In-draft which.

Therefore, the general pattern of the in-draft is sensible and in good accordance with previous studies in the mean.

Influence of Wind and HRR

The 25 simulations run allowed to evaluate the influence of both the HRR and the velocity of the wind. As already explained, the weaker the wind, the higher the domain has to be because we want the plume to escape by the right-hand-side boundary. When the wind velocity is so small that the height H needed implies an unaffordably big domain (such as in the $U_{wind}=1$ m/s case) the model is considered not applicable (referred as "n/a" in Tab. 2. It was therefore not possible to compute the low wind and no-wind cases. In the opposite range, when the wind is too strong compared to the fire, the plume is blown away and there is no in-draft created. A counter-fire ignited in these conditions would be driven by the wind and spread in the same direction as the wildfire. As can be seen in Table 2), the maximum limit in U_{wind} to witness an in-draft increases as the HRR increases. The minimum limit however seems independent on the fire intensity. These results show a good quantitative agreement with Wolnicki [4]. In that model, when the wind velocity is greater than 6m/s, the in-draft is blown away and all the velocities measured are positive. Here, the same effect is observed with $U_{wind}=7$ m/s but not with $U_{wind}=5$ m/s for the biggest fires, which is very similar.

If we take a closer look at the in-draft profiles for different Wind velocities (Fig. 8), the shape of the in-draft profile is affected by the wind. For low wind velocities, the profile is almost straight, whereas it is more wave-shaped for strong winds. The average magnitude of the in-draft is also different: the stronger the wind, the stronger the in-draft (Fig. 9). This result is counter-intuitive: the wind is expected to fight against the in-draft. One possible explanation is that a stronger wind induces a greater plume velocity and therefore more entrainment of the air under it that is the onset of the In-draft. However, in the mean, the influence of the wind is small in this model. A more intuitive result is that the standard deviation bars significantly grow with the wind. It shows that the in-draft becomes less stable when the wind becomes stronger, until reaching the point at which it is completely blown away by the wind.

As for the influence of the HRR, the profiles look very similar and the influence of the fire HRR is not substantial either. One aspect that is worth noticing though, is that an increase in the fire intensity decreases the in-draft in the Intermediate zone but increases it in the Far Field zone. Basically, a bigger fire is expected to generate a stronger in-draft. Yet, according to the model, this statement is only true when the distance to the fire is greater than approximately 60 m.

The main source of error

The discrepancies between the three papers can be explained by the assumptions made to build the model. The most significant error is certainly the dimensionality. The development of vortices in 3D may be expected to be very different than that in 2D, as turbulence is by essence a 3D phenomenon. As already stated, the model predicts an infinite extension of the in-draft as the velocity never becomes positive after the fire. It is a confirmation that a 2D model cannot predict the ideal distance to counter-fire. Indeed, the dimensionality of the domain implies that it is a slice of an infinite fire-line that is modeled. Theoretically, according to [15], the in-draft downstream of a fire depends on the length of this fire-line, as shown on Fig. 11. The longer the line, the longer the orthogonal extension of the in-draft. In fact, the limitation of the in-draft region is strongly affected by the recirculations at the tips of the fire-line. Therefore, an infinite fire-line would theoretically generate an infinite in-draft region. The 2D does not allow a breakup of the distinct vortices by the time the outflow boundary is reached. The computation of the length of the in-draft region is thought to be achievable with a 3D model.

Fig. 11. Influence of the lateral extension of the fire-line (source [15]). For a short fire-line, there is almost no in-draft because of the the recirculation at the extremities. For a longer fire-line however, the in-draft region is bigger

Other sources of error

Many other assumptions were made to build the model, causing additional sources of error. Here are the most important assumptions made. The main fire is here a static symmetrical heat source whereas the rate of spread is a crucial parameter in the use of counter-fire. Transient RANS was used for its relatively low computational cost, but is only able to calculate averaged quantities which signification is still debated in the CFD community. For instance, [16] concluded that Unsteady RANS is unable give the same predictions as LES computations. However, other studies demonstrated that unsteady RANS could provide a good agreement with experimental results, even for complex fows with separation [10, 11]. The $k - \epsilon$ have the advantages of being simple and having coefficients adapted to the problem, but adds a great deal of approximations. Finally, the definition of the open boundary conditions is not optimal either as the pressure profile is strongly affected by the uniform pressure imposed on the boundaries, as can be seen on Fig. 5.

CONCLUSION

The aim of this project was to numerically simulate the in-draft flow in front of a wildfire. The CFD model created was able to generate sensible results having a good agreement with the two previous CFD works. It is the case, for instance, for the increasing of the in-draft velocity with the distance and its stabilization afterwards, as well as the maximum wind velocity at which an in-draft exists. However, the influence of the wind and the fire intensity is poorly depicted. The corresponding variations in the in-draft profile are small and above all reversed compared to other studies. Though, only experimental data could validate the results. All these non sensible results come from the fact that the domain only has two dimensions. A lot of efforts have been made to improve the boundary conditions as well as the turbulence modeling, but a 2D model seems unable to predict the behavior a wildfire subject to a cross wind. To conclude, the most important output of paper is that 3D simulations could potentially be able to provide accurate results.

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